

Water in olive oil microemulsions as medium for CdS nanoparticles synthesis

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Abstract : The present work provides a potentially efficient and a simple chemical route for the synthesis of CdS nanoparticles with spherical shape in quaternary sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS)/1-butanol/olive/water microemulsion systems. The structures and morphologies of CdS nanoparticles were characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), UV-Vis spectra and infrared spectroscopy. The influence of the molar ratio of water to surfactant (ω_o) on the size of the CdS nanoparticles was studied. With the increase of ω_o , the particles size becomes larger. The role of surfactant, in the formation of CdS nanoparticles was also discussed in detail.

Keywords : Cadmium sulfide, nanoparticle, transmission electron microscope, infrared spectroscopy.

Introduction

Nanoparticles have attracted considerable attention due to their unique properties, which are not present in bulk materials¹⁻³. CdS nanoparticles, in particular, have been extensively studied due to their potential applications such as field effect transistors, light emitting diodes, photocatalysts and biological sensors⁴⁻⁶. These exciting applications have focused attention on the size and shape control and organization of CdS nanoparticles^{7,8}. Many synthetic methods have been employed to prepare CdS nanoparticles including soft chemical reaction, solid-state reaction, sol-gel process, sonochemical preparation^{9,10}, microwave heating¹¹, photoetching¹² and reverse micelle¹³. In this investigation, we have developed a method to produce CdS nanoparticles of small sizes using microemulsions systems.

Synthesis of nanoparticles in water-in-oil microemulsions, can yield particles nearly monodisperse in size. In addition, variation in the water drop size of the microemulsion system gives nanoparticles of controlled mean size. Hence the aforementioned size-dependent properties are accessible by simple control of particle size. These microemulsions are a thermodynamically stable dispersion of nanometer-sized water drops in a continuous oil medium¹⁴. The stability of these drops is attrib-

uted to the presence of adsorbed surfactant molecules at the oil-water interface of the drop. The drops undergo Brownian motion, thus colliding with each other and occasionally coalescing. Reactants predissolved in the water drops undergo chemical reaction in this process. Subsequently, the reaction product nucleates to form a nanoparticle inside the drop.

The literature concerning the preparation of CdS nanoparticles by use of water-in-oil microemulsion is quite scarce^{15,16}. Thus, our intension was to enrich our knowledge on some structural aspects of such microemulsion systems in relation to the formation of nanoparticles. In this paper, CdS nanoparticles were prepared in sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS)/1-butanol/olive/water microemulsion. The morphological feature of the nanoparticles was investigated by TEM, UV-Vis spectra and infrared spectroscopy. The role of surfactant in the formation of CdS nanoparticles and the influence of the molar ratio of water to surfactant (ω_o) on the size of particles were also discussed.

Experimental

Materials :

Virgin olive oil was obtained from the local market. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and 1-butanol (99% pure)

was purchased from Sigma. Cadmium chloride and sodium sulfide were purchased from Merck. These reagents were used as received. The water used in all the experiments is deionized one.

Synthesis of CdS nanoparticles :

To prepare the microemulsion, SDS, *n*-butyl alcohol and olive oil were used as surfactant, cosurfactant and oil phase, respectively. Then the oil phase, surfactant and cosurfactant were mixed by magnetically stirring until the mixture became transparent. Divide the mixture into two parts, and the two different microemulsions were prepared as follows : the CdCl₂ aqueous (0.012 M) was added into one of the parts then the microemulsion of CdCl₂ was obtained; the Na₂S.9H₂O aqueous (0.012 M) was added into the other part of mixture until the mixture became transparent, then the reverse microemulsion of Na₂S was prepared. All experimental processes were under magnetic stirring. The two microemulsions were mixed and magnetically stirred at room temperature of 26 °C for about 15 min.

Characterization :

TEM was used to examine the morphology of the CdS nanoparticles on a JEOL transmission electron microscope (model : JEM-1230, Japan). The UV-Vis spectra were recorded in a range from 200 to 1000 nm using a Perkin-Elmer UV-1601PC UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) measurements were carried out using Perkin-Elmer Spectrum1 FT-IR. IR spectra of the samples were obtained in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Results and discussion

The microdroplets in the microemulsion are in spherical shape with diameter from 10 to 100 nm¹⁷. Due to the controllable water pool, reversed microemulsions are particularly favorable for the preparation of monodisperse nanoparticles with various particle sizes. In the method of synthesizing nanoparticles using reverse microemulsions, different reactants in different water nuclei exchange each other and the reaction takes place. Due to the coalescence of the reverse micelles, exchange of the materials in the water droplets occurs, which causes a reaction between the cores^{18,19}. And in this step, an instant dimer can be formed while the droplets collide each

other. Then the instant dimer provides water channel for the two droplets to exchange reactants at this moment. Just during the uninterrupted combination and separation, the reaction takes place and then molecules engender. More and more resultant molecules adhere on the nucleus to form a particle at last. Since the nucleus grows only in the microwater droplets of microemulsion and the droplets have a certain shape and size, the shape and size of resultant particles are determined by the water droplets. SDS and 1-butanol adheres to the surface of the nanoparticles served as a protective layer to prevent from collision and amalgamation of the droplets^{20–24}. So ω_0 is a key parameter in determining the dimensions of microemulsion droplets. Diameter of the droplets increases with the increase of ω_0 , so the final particles size varies with ω_0 and the phenomenon of the agglomeration occurs with the increase of ω_0 .

Fig. 1 shows typical TEM images of the CdS nanoparticles prepared at reverse microemulsion system with different ω_0 . It follows that the average size of the nanoparticles increases with increasing ω_0 . We also can find from this figure that the morphology of the particles is almost homogeneous.

Fig. 2 depicts the effect of ω_0 on the particle size of CdS synthesized in the present investigation. One can see that, $\omega_0 = 5$ is suitable to get the particle size 16 nm. It was significant to increase ω_0 from 5 to 15 as the particles increases gradually in this response. From the findings, I have concluded that, surfactant and cosurfactant with $\omega_0 = 10$ and 15 is unable to prevent the agglomeration of CdS particles. On the other hand, in synthesis with $\omega_0 = 5$, it is possible to get fine CdS particles by showing proper capping activity. Owing to formation of the finest particle size with $\omega_0 = 5$ in this work, the further results are presented for this case only.

Fig. 3 shows the UV-Vis optical absorption spectrum of CdS nanoparticles. We can estimate that an UV-Vis optical absorption excitonic peak of the nanoparticles is at 370 nm, and shows a blue shift from that of bulk CdS (530 nm) crystals. This result is in agreement with the value of the reported literatures¹. From the spectra, we also estimated the band gap of CdS nanoparticles to be 2.70 eV. Compared with that of bulk CdS (2.42 eV)²⁵, this clearly indicates the presence of quantum-size effects in the prepared CdS nanoparticles.

Fig. 4. IR spectra of the CdS nanoparticles in SDS/1-butanol/olive oil/water microemulsion with $\omega_0 = 5$.

nanoparticles serve as a protective layer to prevent from collision and amalgamation of the droplets. This microemulsion has its own advantage and is subjected to wider use in preparing nanoparticles.

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